

Studies in Quinones. Part III. Azonaphthols. (Monophenylhydrazones of 1,2-Naphthaquinone)

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Nine substituted phenylhydrazines have been allowed to react with 1,2-naphthaquinone to yield products that behave both as azonaphthols and monophenylhydrazones of the naphthaquinone.

The present investigation is an extension of the work published in earlier parts¹ of this series and includes the study of the reaction of 1,2-naphthaquinone with 4-nitro-(I), 2-bromo-4-nitro-(II), 2-chloro-4-nitro-(III), 4-chloro-2-nitro-(IV), 2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-(V), 2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-(VI), 4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-(VII), 6-bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-(VIII), and 6-chloro-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-(IX) phenylhydrazines.

The structure of the condensation products has been established by reducing their alkaline solutions with sodium hydrosulphite and isolating the 2-aminonaphthol, indicating that out of the two carbonyl groups in the quinone, only carbonyl group at position 2 takes part in the condensation with nitrophenylhydrazines.

The products not only form salts with aqueous sodium hydroxide and acetyl derivatives with acetic anhydride (like phenolic compounds), but also furnish dihydrazones with phenylhydrazine (like ketonic or quinonoid compound). These reactions indicate that the products are tautomeric in character.

The azonaphthols, deep red to dark chocolate in shade, are slightly soluble in ethanol and more readily in acetic acid from which these can be crystallised.

EXPERIMENTAL

Azonaphthols.—Following the procedure reported in the previous communications¹, these were obtained by condensing nitrophenylhydrazines with 1,2-naphthaquinone. The acetyl and phenylhydrazine derivatives of the azonaphthols were prepared by following the procedure described earlier¹.

Analytical data and characteristics of azonaphthols obtained from different phenylhydrazines and 1,2-naphthaquinone, together with those of their acetyl and phenylhydrazine derivatives, are recorded in Tables I and II respectively.

TABLE I

Azonaphthols from 1,2-naphthoquinone and substituted phenylhydrazines.

S.No.	Phenyl-hydrazine.	Azonaphthol (2'-azo-1-ol).	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	I	4-Nitro-	238°	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃	N : 14.12%	14.33%
2	II	2-Bromo-4-nitro-	233°(d)	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	Br : 21.31	21.50
3	III	2-Chloro-4-nitro-	236°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.61	10.84
4	IV	4-Chloro-2-nitro-	218°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 10.77	10.84
5	V	2-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-	215°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.12	9.53
6	VI	2-Bromo-4,6-dinitro-	210°	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 18.96	19.18
7	VII	4,6-Dinitro-3-methyl-	232°	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₄	N : 16.19	16.91
8	VIII	6-Bromo-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	228°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	Br : 18.28	18.56
9	IX	6-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-3-methyl-	237°	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 9.01	9.18

(d) denotes decomposition.

TABLE II

*S. No.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Acetyl derivatives.					
1	183°	Deep red	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	N : 12.30%	12.54%
2	181°	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Br	Br : 19.13	19.32
3	183°	Red	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.44	9.61
4	168°	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 9.48	9.61
5	185°	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.74	8.56
6	188°	Deep red	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 17.22	17.43
7	204°	Red	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₄	N : 14.42	14.21
8	188°	Deep red	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₄ Br	Br : 17.20	16.91
9	195°	"	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 8.39	8.28
Phenylhydrazones.					
1	263°	Red	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	N : 18.11%	18.27
2	242°	Orange-red	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Br	Br : 17.18	17.31
3	255°	"	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 8.29	8.60
4	245°	"	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 8.43	8.60
5	249°	Orange-yellow	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 7.50	7.67
6	232°	Red	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 15.57	15.78
7	265°	Brown-red	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₆	N : 18.81	19.00
8	262°	"	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₆ Br	Br : 15.51	15.35
9	273°	Deep red	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₆ Cl	Cl : 7.34	7.45

*The number of azonaphthol corresponds to those listed in Table I.

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